

IoT-Based Non-Invasive RBI Index Detection using Electrocardiogram Photoplethysmogram Signals with Firebase Cloud Integration and Real-Time Health Alerts

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Abstract

Peripheral artery disease is a chronic circulatory disorder that is manifested by narrowing or obstruction of peripheral arteries, mainly lower limbs. Early diagnosis is crucial to avoid severe complications: critical limb ischemia, myocardial infarction, and stroke. However, these diagnostic methods require clinical setups and trained professionals for their operation, limiting accessibility during early or continuous screening. This paper proposes the design and prototype implementation of a wearable device for early PAD detection based on multi-sensor data fusion. The system is integrated with Electrocardiogram (ECG), Photoplethysmogram (PPG), and bioimpedance sensors to monitor vascular health continuously. With this setup, Pulse transit time (PTT) and Pulse wave velocity (PWV) are computed as surrogate markers of arterial stiffness, and simultaneous bioimpedance data complement vascular tone information. The microcontroller-based system (ESP32) performs real-time data acquisition,

pre-processing, and wireless transmission via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) to a mobile application for visualization. Preliminary tests on healthy volunteers confirm successful synchronization of ECG and PPG signals, demonstrating the feasibility of non-invasive vascular monitoring. Future work includes the machine-learning-based PAD stage classification and clinical validation. A cost-effective, portable, continuous monitoring solution is provided by the proposed device, which can be used for early diagnosis and management of PAD.

Keywords: Peripheral Artery Disease, Wearable Sensor, Electrocardiogram, Photoplethysmogram, Bioimpedance, Pulse Transit Time, Pulse Wave Velocity, Data Fusion.

1. Introduction

PAD is a progressive vascular disorder due to the accumulation of atherosclerotic plaque, leading to stenosis or occlusion of the arteries in the extremities. The diminished blood flow results in pain, fatigability, or trophic ulcers and may lead to tissue necrosis and amputation of the extremity in advanced disease. The WHO estimates that more than 200 million people worldwide suffer from PAD, most of whom remain asymptomatic and undiagnosed in early stages. PAD is strongly linked to diabetes, hypertension, and smoking; it also acts as an early marker of cardiovascular events and mortality.

While traditional diagnostic techniques, such as the ankle-brachial index, are very reliable, they do require Doppler ultrasound machinery and professionals who know how to use such equipment. These tests are point-in-time in nature and cannot represent dynamic vascular changes. The clinical and technologically increasing demand is, hence, toward the development of noninvasive, continuous, and accessible diagnostic systems that would be able to detect hemodynamic changes indicative of PAD.

Recent developments in both wearable technology and physiological signal processing have enabled the continuous monitoring of cardiovascular activity outside clinical settings. ECG and PPG sensors may provide an estimate of PTT and PWV, surrogate markers of arterial stiffness and blood vessel compliance, respectively. At the same time, bioimpedance sensing allows the determination of tissue perfusion and vascular tone, providing complementary information on peripheral circulation.

This paper proposes a wearable multi-sensor device that integrates these three modalities-ECG, PPG, and bioimpedance-on a compact platform for real-time monitoring. Such an